

FACTORS AFFECTING TEACHERS JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS: BASIS FOR PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The overall objective of this study is to create an enhancement program for secondary teachers on ways of improving teaching and identifying areas of development. The study employed the qualitative data analysis of exploratory methods in gathering the data needed. The researcher uses thematic analysis in order to have the whole numbers of population used in the research. By reviewing the data, the researcher identifies the theme that grasps out repeatedly within the data. Using thematic analysis, researcher find's out that it is very useful about finding out about teacher's job experiences, views and opinions. That's why thematic analysis is very suitable in understanding teachers' experiences and views and helps the researcher to create an enhancement program for secondary teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the most important factors that has a direct relation to the development of the society from the starting and continues to assume the same role as long as society exists. Education is also a process by which man transmits his experience, new findings and values accumulated for several centuries in his struggle for survival. It is a base for socio – economic, cultural and political development of a country. It enables individuals and society to make full participation in the development process by acquiring knowledge, skills, ability and attitudes.

According to Panda and Mohanty (2008) good teachers are essential for the effective functioning of the education system and for improving the quality of the learning process. Job satisfaction enables teachers to put their maximum effort up on their work. The maintenance of high satisfaction and morale has long been an important objective for educators. Teachers develop

performance style characteristics to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. A teacher is, therefore, likely to act in a way that maximises the use of his/her aptitudes. Similarly, teacher's positive attitudes towards teaching and higher objectives determine their positive perception of the environment. An effective teacher's development design should have an exhaustive measure of these factors so as to encourage necessary skills and attitudes among prospective teachers. The exclusive weight age to knowledge alone should be dispensed with in support of more activity oriented programs which have direct behaviour on actual classroom situations (UNESCO, 2009).

The teachers should realise that it is not only necessary to be honest but one must make attempts to make others honest for a better society. On the other hand, the discussion induced most of the teachers to love honesty which was a hidden value for developing a positive attitude towards the teaching profession (Kumar, 2009).

As to Riaz (2008), factors that influence teachers' job performance were aptitude, attitude, subject mastery, teaching methodology, personal characteristics, the classroom environment, personality, relations with students, preparation and planning, effectiveness in presenting subject matters, relations with other staff, self-improvement, relations with parents and community, self-confidence, intellect, teaching techniques, teaching competence demonstrated, motivation of teachers and teacher's attitude toward the students. The government of Ethiopia expressed its commitments for the improvement of quality education in many educational conferences and events. Then the aim of continuous professional development (CPD) was to improve the performance of teachers in the classroom and improve student achievement. It was a career –a long process of improving knowledge, skills and attitudes – centred on the local context and, particularly, classroom practice. All teachers must be actively engaged in: (a) their own learning process (b) working with their colleagues (c) identifying their own needs and (d) the wide range of activities, formal and informal, that brings about improvement of their own practice and the practice of others (MOE, 2009 b).

Furthermore, MoE had introduced a program called general generation quality improvement package (GEQIP) which was designed to improve the quality of education. As the major input of education quality, teachers are widely recognized as a critical factor influencing education quality. Thus, teachers' professional development was the most determining factors to guarantee education quality. The ministry of education has given priority for continuous professional development (CPD) believing that it is the right of teachers as well as of a great value for national development especially in the areas of teachers' beliefs, attitudes and practices, needed to enhance students' learning (UNESCO,2009).

Therefore, within the framework of education and training policy (TGE, 2010) the education sector development program (ESDP) was launched as a twenty-year education sector plan with one of the main priorities, quality improvement at all levels of the educational system after extensive study by the ministry of education. This study revealed important factors that affect teachers' job performance such as, difficult conditions of work environment; weak pre-service preparation and lack of continuous professional development, and weak management and leadership. Based on the recommendations and indicative action plan presented in the study report, a task force was

established to produce the national framework for the teacher education system overhaul (TESO) and the program has been implemented (MoE, 2009).

The study of V. Robles (2018) established the Teacher's Job Performance in Public Secondary School in Tanauan City Division is very effective as the basis for gathering the data of this study. As she compiled and interpreted those factors affecting the teacher's job performance negatively and positively in the said year, she utilized the essence of the teachers experiences, views, and opinions in the academic field of teaching.

Furthermore, the researcher aims to develop an enhancement program for public secondary teachers on ways of improving teaching and identifying areas of development. It aims to enhance the teachers' ability to become effective in teaching. It also aims to provide an appropriate and well-planned program for teachers which includes giving them opportunities to grow and is designed to meet the diverse needs of all learners. This enhancement program is the key in meeting today's educational demand.

Research Questions

This study is an attempt to identify the factors affecting teacher's job performance in public secondary schools: Basis for proposed enhancement program.

Specifically, this study would like to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the public secondary school teachers under study in terms of
 - 1.1 Length of teaching experience
 - 1.2 Educational attainment; and
 - 1.3 In service Training Attended?

2. What are the factors affecting teacher's job performance as perceived by school principals and by the teachers themselves in terms of:
 - 2.1 Career Related Factors
 - 2.2 Non Career Related Factors

3. What is the level of effectiveness of teachers as perceived by school principals and by the teachers themselves in terms of:
 - 3.1 Teaching Methodology
 - 3.2 Current Status of Teachers Job Performance
 - 3.3 The Improvement of Teacher's Job Performance
 - 3.4 Teacher's Subject Matter Mastery

4. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of two sets of respondents on teachers' performance in teaching?

5. Based on the findings of the study, what Teacher Effectiveness Enhancement program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the qualitative data analysis of exploratory methods in gathering the data needed. The researcher uses thematic analysis in order to have the whole numbers of population used in the research. The study of V. Robles (2018) about Teachers Job Performance in Public Secondary School in Tanauan City Division which is the former colleague of the proponent was used to have the body's of data needed in the study in assessing the proposed enhancement program for the teachers since the study uses non-probability sampling the selection of participants is not statistically random in other words the selection of school participants is based on the discretion and judgement of the researchers rather on the predetermined process. It is more important to get the richness and depth of the data than the generalized ability of the findings. By reviewing the data the researcher identifies the theme that crops out repeatedly within the data. Using thematic analysis, researchers find out that it is very useful about finding out about a teacher's job experiences, views and opinions. That's why thematic analysis is very suitable in understanding teachers' experiences or views for something, since thematic analysis is an exploratory process of the data of V. Robles (2018) which is used by the proponents has the strong hold to create an enhancement program for the teachers.

There are multiple factors that affect the performance of teachers. These may include attitude, subject mastery, teaching methodology, personal characteristics, managerial approach, motivation, relation with community, student behaviour, etc. However, the scope of this study will focus on attitude, subject mastery, teaching methodology and personal characteristics of factors and to identify the factors that affect the performance of teachers and to suggest possible solutions that could be taken to enhance performance of teachers. This study is limited to some selected public secondary schools of Tanauan City Division. It covers the teacher's profile which includes the length of teaching experience, in-service training and educational attainment that make this study manageable to various constraints of what affect teachers' job performance.

RESULTS

The results deal with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered with regard to the teacher's job performance in public secondary schools of Tanauan City Division that assessing the factors affecting to teachers job performance as basis for proposed enhancement program.

Specifically, the purpose of this study is to find the answer in the following queries.

- 1. On the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Length of Teaching Experience, Educational Attainment, and In Service Training Attended.**

Table 1.1
Profile of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Length of Teaching Experience.

Length of Teaching Experience in years	Frequency	%
1-5	113	57.36
6-10	40	20.30
11-15	16	8.12
16-20	22	11.17
21-25	1	0.51
More than 25 years	5	2.54
Total	197	100

Majority of the teachers have teaching experience from 1 year to 5 years as indicated by the frequency count of 113 or 57.36 percent followed by 6 years to 10 years with 40 or 20.30 percent, then 16 years to 20 years with of 22 or 11.17 percent, next is 11 years to 15 years and more than 25 years with frequency count of 16 or 8.12 percent and 5 or 2.54 percent, respectively. The least group belongs to 21 years to 25 years with only 1 respondent or 0.51 percent.

From the findings it was revealed that majority of the public secondary school teachers were 1 year to 5 years in teaching service. This implies that they are in their early ages which can be able to use modern method of teaching to make it more interesting and attractive to student and also teachers who are energetic, with vigor to utilize modern approaches of teaching.

Table 1.2
Profile of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Educational Attainment.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	%
Bachelor's Degree	64	32.49
Currently Pursuing Graduate Studies (Master's Degree)	42	21.32
Master's Degree	79	40.10
Currently Pursuing Graduate Studies (Doctoral Degree)	3	1.52
Doctoral Degree	9	4.57
Total:	197	100

Majority of the teachers are masters' degree as denoted by the frequency count 79 or 40.10 percent, followed by the bachelor's degree with 64 or 32.49 percent next is currently pursuing master's degree with 42 or 21.32 percent and the teachers reached doctoral degree with 9 or 4.57 percent. The least group of teachers are currently pursuing doctoral degree with 3 or 1.52 percent.

The teachers who attained master's degree obtained **40.10 %** on rank number **1**. This implies that many teachers choose to return school and obtain master's degree that allows honing their abilities and becoming expert educators.

Table 1.3
Profile of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Numbers of In Service Training Attended.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	%
National	59	10.35
Regional	84	14.74
Division	131	22.98
District	97	17.02
School	198	34.91
Total	569	100

Majority of the teachers attended in service training's in school as indicated with a frequency count of 198 or 34.91 percent, followed by the division level with 131 or 22.98 percent next is district and regional level with a frequency count of 97 or 17.02 and 84 or 14.74. The least indicator is national level with 59 or 10.35.

This implies that teachers were well updated with better ways of undertaking their subjects. But more attendance in higher level is required to enable them undertake the same at least one a year.

2. The factors affecting teacher's job performance as perceived by school principals and by the teachers themselves in terms of Career Related factors and Non Career Related Factors.

2.1 The factors affecting teacher's job performance as perceived by school principals and by teachers themselves under Career Related Factors.

Table 2.1.1
Career Related Factors
(Deadlines / Time Pressures)

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Lack of time in preparing lesson plans, related instructional	3.00	Moderately Stressful	3	4.20	Highly Stressful	1	3.60	Highly Stressful	1

devices, testing materials and other school forms.									
2. Lack of time in checking tests, exercises, activities and other written output.	3.31	Moderately Stressful	1	3.63	Highly Stressful	3	3.47	Moderately Stressful	2
3. Coping up with lesson/activities which are behind schedule.	3.15	Moderately Stressful	2	3.75	Highly Stressful	2	3.45	Moderately Stressful	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.15	Moderately Stressful		3.86	Highly Stressful		3.51	Highly Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers' job performance under career related factors in terms of deadlines and time pressures. School Heads and Teachers perceived that they are lack in time in preparing lesson plans, related instructional devices, testing materials and other school forms which obtained the weighted mean of **3.60** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**. This implies that that teacher must boost their competency or their potential in handling their jobs and producing the best results. It is the ability in executing duties which are related to necessary activities.

Moreover, they are lack of time in checking tests, exercises, activities and other written output which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.47** with moderately stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. This implies that teachers must learn the proper time management and prioritizing works to promote less stress and panic in working.

Furthermore, they are coping up with lesson/activities which are behind schedule was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.45** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**. This implies that the teacher must be prepared and benefited by the desired changes through improvement.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.86** compare to the school heads perception with **3.15** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **2.51** implies that the school heads and teachers career related factors in deadlines and a time pressure is highly stressful. This implies that the teacher needs to enhance their competency which is a criterion possessed by an individual to be able to present excellent results.

**Table 2.1.2
Career Related Factors
(Workloads/Extra-Curricular Activities)**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Too heavy workloads or teaching loads.	3.23	Moderately Stressful	2	3.94	Highly Stressful	1	3.59	Highly Stressful	2
2. Too many school responsibilities	3.69	Highly Stressful	1	3.55	Highly Stressful	3	3.62	Highly Stressful	1
3. Teaching non- major subjects	2.23	Less Stressful	3	3.70	Highly Stressful	2	2.97	Moderately Stressful	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.05	Moderately Stressful		3.73	Highly Stressful		3.39	Moderately Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers' job performance under career related factors in terms of workloads and extra - curricular activities. School Heads and Teachers perceived that they have too many school responsibilities which obtained the weighted mean of **3.62** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**. This implies that the teachers should be well oriented that their professional accountability or responsibility of teacher educators includes instructional and non-instructional responsibilities.

Moreover, they find their workloads or teaching loads too heavy which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.59** with highly stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**.

Furthermore, teaching non- major subjects was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **2.97** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.73** compare to the school heads perception with **3.05** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.39** implies that the school heads and teachers career related factors in workloads and extra -curricular activities are moderately stressful. This implies that a high positive relation between professional commitment hast a direct effect to the job satisfaction.

**Table 2.1.3
Career Related Factors
(School Management)**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Inconsistency in rules/policies	3.77	Highly Stressful	1	3.70	Highly Stressful	2	3.74	Highly Stressful	1

2. Too much or poor supervision	2.92	Moderately Stressful	3	3.76	Highly Stressful	1	3.34	Moderately Stressful	3
3. Lack of consultation/communication in decision making	3.31	Moderately Stressful	2	3.69	Highly Stressful	3	3.50	Highly Stressful	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.33	Moderately Stressful		3.72	Highly Stressful		3.53	Highly Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers' job performance under career related factors in terms of school management. School Heads and Teachers perceived that there is an inconsistency in rules and policies which obtained the weighted mean of **3.74** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, there is a lack of consultation and communication in decision making which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.50** with highly stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**.

Furthermore, too much or poor supervision was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.34** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.72** compare to the school heads perception with **3.33** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.53** implies that the school heads and teachers career related factors in school management are highly stressful. This implies that the school leader influences teachers and their staffs for successful operations of teaching and learning in the school.

Table 2.1.4
Career Related Factors
(Management of Student's Behavior)

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Classroom discipline	3.23	Moderately Stressful	4	3.78	Highly Stressful	4	3.51	Highly Stressful	4
2. Counseling misbehaved students	3.38	Moderately Stressful	2.5	3.87	Highly Stressful	3	3.63	Highly Stressful	3
3. Checking student's poor study habits	3.54	Highly Stressful	1	3.88	Highly Stressful	2	3.71	Highly Stressful	2
4. Upgrading students' poor performance through remedial teaching	3.38	Moderately Stressful	2.5	4.05	Highly Stressful	1	3.72	Highly Stressful	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.38	Moderately Stressful		3.89	Highly Stressful		3.64	Highly Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers' job performance under career related factors in terms of management of student's behavior. School Heads and Teachers perceived that there upgrading student's poor performance through remedial teaching which obtained the weighted mean of **3.72** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, the checking of student's poor study habits which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.71** with highly stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. The counseling of misbehaved students obtained a weighted mean score of **3.63** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **3**.

Furthermore, classroom discipline was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.51** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **4**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.89** compare to the school heads perception with **3.38** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.64** implies that the school heads and teachers career related factors in management of student's behavior are highly stressful. This implies that a teacher should make use of personality and personal influence and maintain a personal attitude in maintaining excellent discipline in the classroom.

2.1.5. The factors affecting teacher's job performance as perceived by school principals and by teachers themselves under career related factors in terms of physical environment and school facilities.

**Table 2.1.5
Career Related Factors
(Physical Environment/Facilities)**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Oversized classes	3.38	Moderately Stressful	1	3.97	Highly Stressful	3	3.68	Highly Stressful	1
2. Poor classroom conditions	3.15	Moderately Stressful	2	4.10	Highly Stressful	2	3.63	Highly Stressful	2
3. Unavailability of some facilities for basic needs of students/teachers like comfort rooms, drinking faucets, etc.	2.77	Moderately Stressful	3	4.13	Highly Stressful	1	3.45	Moderately Stressful	3
Average weighted mean	3.10	Moderately Stressful		4.07	Highly Stressful		3.59	Highly Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers' job performance under career related factors in terms of physical environment/school facilities. School Heads and Teachers perceived that

oversized classes is a factor that affecting teacher’s job performance which obtained the weighted mean of **3.68** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, a poor classroom conditions is also a factor which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.63** with highly stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**.

Furthermore, unavailability of some facilities for basic needs of students and teachers like comfort rooms, drinking faucets and etc. was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.45** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **4.07** compare to the school heads perception with **3.10** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.59** implies that the school heads and teachers career related factors in physical environment and school facilities are highly stressful. This implies that teachers and students work best in a comfortable and inviting environment, it can make the teacher easily accessible and approachable or create and additional barrier between the teacher and the students.

2. 1. 6. The factors affecting teacher’s job performance as perceived by school principals and by teachers themselves under career related factors in terms of work relationship.

**Table 2.1.6
Career Related Factors
(Work Relationship)**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Relationship with superiors.	2.69	Moderately Stressful	1	3.97	Highly Stressful	4	3.33	Moderately Stressful	1
2. Relationship with other teachers.	1.92	Less Stressful	4	4.10	Highly Stressful	3	3.01	Moderately Stressful	4
3. Relationship with the students.	2.38	Less Stressful	2	4.13	Highly Stressful	1.5	3.26	Moderately Stressful	2
4. Relationship with the community.	2.00	Less Stressful	3	4.13	Highly Stressful	1.5	3.07	Moderately Stressful	3
Average Weighted Mean	2.25	Less Stressful		4.08	Highly Stressful		3.17	Moderately Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers’ job performance under career related factors in terms of work relationship. School Heads and Teachers perceived that the relationship with superiors affect their job performance which obtained the weighted mean of **3.33** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, the relationship with the students which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.26** with moderately stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. The relationship with the

community obtained a weighted mean score of **3.07** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**.

Furthermore, relationship with the other teachers was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.01** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **4**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **4.08** compare to the school heads perception with **2.25** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.17** implies that the school heads and teachers career related factors in work relationship are moderately stressful. This implies that teachers working condition affect their ability to provide quality education.

2.2 The factors affecting teacher’s job performance as perceived by school principals and by teachers themselves under Non- Career Related Factors.

**Table 2.2.1.
Non Career Related Factors
(Financial Problems)**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Low Salary/ income to support the basic needs of the family.	3.92	Highly Stressful	1	3.68	Highly Stressful	1	3.80	Highly Stressful	1
2. Non-payment of some financial obligations/debts.	3.85	Highly Stressful	2	3.28	Moderately Stressful	4	3.57	Highly Stressful	2
3. Lack of money to pursue graduate studies.	2.85	Moderately Stressful	4	3.43	Moderately Stressful	3	3.14	Moderately Stressful	4
4. Lack of money to attend seminars/training for professional growth.	3.31	Moderately Stressful	3	3.52	Highly Stressful	2	3.42	Moderately Stressful	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.48	Moderately Stressful		3.61	Highly Stressful		3.48	Moderately Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers’ job performance under non- career related factors in terms of financial problems. School Heads and Teachers perceived that low salary/income to support the basic need to the family is a factor that affects the teacher’s job performance which obtained the weighted mean of **3.80** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, the non-payment of some financial obligations and debts which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.57** with highly stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. The lack of money to attend seminars and training for professional growth obtained a weighted mean score of **3.42** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **3**.

Furthermore, lack of money to pursue graduate studies was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.14** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **4**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.61** compare to the school heads perception with **3.48** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.48** implies that the school heads and teachers non career related factors in financial problems are moderately stressful. This implies that motivation of teachers helps to retain at their work places and it includes” materials and psychological needs” as pay on its own increase motivation among teachers.

Table 2.2.2.
Non Career Related Factors
(Conflicts at Home)

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Conflicts among the members of the family.	2.85	Moderately Stressful	3	3.68	Highly Stressful	1	3.23	Moderately Stressful	3
2. Separation/ distance from the family	2.46	Less Stressful	5	3.28	Moderately Stressful	5	2.87	Moderately Stressful	5
3. Conflicts with neighbors or some people in the community.	3.31	Moderately Stressful	2	3.43	Moderately Stressful	4	3.37	Moderately Stressful	2
4. Failure to attend to some gathering due to conflicts at work.	2.77	Moderately Stressful	4	3.52	Highly Stressful	3	3.15	Moderately Stressful	4
5. Failure to attend to some family gatherings due to conflicts at work.	3.38	Moderately Stressful	1	3.61	Highly Stressful	2	3.50	Highly Stressful	1
Average Weighted Mean	2.95	Moderately Stressful		3.50	Highly Stressful		3.22	Moderately Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers’ job performance under non- career related factors in terms of conflicts at home. School Heads and Teachers perceived that failure to attend some family gatherings due to conflicts at work is a factor that affects the teacher’s job performance which obtained the weighted mean of **3.50** with verbal interpretation of highly stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, the conflicts with neighbors or some people in the community which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.37** with moderately stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. The conflicts among the members of the family obtained a weighted mean score of **3.23** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**. The failure to attend some gathering due

to conflicts at work obtained a weighted mean score of **3.15** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful.

Furthermore, the separation or distance from the family was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **2.87** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **5**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.50** compare to the school heads perception with **2.95** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.22** implies that the school heads and teachers non career related factors in conflicts at home are moderately stressful.

**Table 2.2.3
Non Career Related Factors
(Health Disorders)**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Psychological disorders such as heightened emotions, anxiety and forgetfulness.	2.69	Moderately Stressful	1	3.80	Highly Stressful	1	3.25	Moderately Stressful	1
2. Physiological disorders such as illnesses and deformities.	2.62	Moderately Stressful	2	3.72	Highly Stressful	2	3.17	Moderately Stressful	2
3. Behavioral disorders such as bad habits and vices.	1.85	Less Stressful	3	3.48	Moderately Stressful	3	2.67	Moderately Stressful	3
Average Weighted Mean	2.38	Less Stressful		3.67	Highly Stressful		3.03	Moderately Stressful	

This table shows the factors affecting teachers’ job performance under non- career related factors in terms of health disorders. School Heads and Teachers perceived that psychological disorders such as heightened emotions, anxiety and forgetfulness is factor that affects the teacher’s job performance which obtained the weighted mean of **3.25** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **1**.

Moreover, physiological disorders such as illnesses and deformities which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.17** with moderately stressful verbal interpretation on rank number **2**.

Furthermore, the behavioral disorders such as bad habits and vices was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **2.67** with verbal interpretation of moderately stressful on rank number **3**.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.67** compare to the school heads perception with **2.38** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.03** implies that the school heads and teachers non career related factors in health disorders are moderately stressful.

3. The level of effectiveness of teacher’s as perceived by school heads and by the teachers themselves in terms of Teaching Methodology, Current Status of Teacher’s Job Performance, The Improvement of Teacher’s Job Performance, and Teacher’s Subject Matter Mastery.

**Table 3.1
Teaching Methodology**

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Teachers’ teaching methodology is good.	3.62	Agree	4	4.19	Agree	1	3.91	Agree	2
2. Teachers have integrating subject content with daily activities make teaching learning process easy.	3.69	Agree	2	4.08	Agree	5	3.89	Agree	4
3. They use different techniques to teach.	3.69	Agree	2	4.11	Agree	4	3.90	Agree	3
4. They make easy their teaching by integrating subject matter with daily examples.	3.69	Agree	2	4.14	Agree	3	3.92	Agree	1
5. They identify the student learning as their primary responsibility.	3.46	Neutral	5	4.15	Agree	2	3.81	Agree	5
Average weighted mean	3.63	Agree		4.13	Agree		3.89	Agree	

This table shows the level of effectiveness of teacher’s in terms of teaching methodology. School Heads and Teachers perceived that teachers make easy their teaching by integrating subject matter with daily examples which obtained the weighted mean of **3.92** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **1**.

Moreover, a teachers’ teaching methodology is good which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.91** with agree verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. The use of different techniques to

teach obtained weighted mean score of 3.90 with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number 3. Teachers have integrating subject content with daily activities make teaching learning process easy obtained a weighted mean of **3.89** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number 4.

Furthermore, they identify the students learning as their primary responsibility was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **3.81** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number 5.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **4.13** compare to the school heads perception with **3.63** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.89** implies that the schools heads and teachers level of effectiveness in terms of teaching methodology are agreeable.

Table 3.2
Current Status of Teachers' Job Performance

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. The status of teachers' participation in school teachers' development program.	3.85	Agree	2	4.31	Agree	1	4.08	Agree	1
2. Participation in collaboration research has enhanced their teachers development program	3.15	Neutral	5	4.23	Agree	3.5	3.69	Agree	3
3. Residential problems of teachers affect their performance.	3.46	Neutral	4	4.26	Agree	2	3.86	Agree	2
4. Language of instruction affects teachers' performance.	3.77	Agree	3	4.23	Agree	3.5	3.64	Agree	4
5. They try to maintain a careful and clean personal appearance.	4.08	Agree	1	1.01	Strongly Disagree	5	2.55	Neutral	5
Average weighted mean	3.66	Agree		3.61	Agree		3.56	Agree	

This table shows the level of effectiveness of teacher's in terms current status of teachers job performance. School Heads and Teachers perceived that status of teacher's participation in

school teachers development program makes them effective which obtained the weighted mean of **4.08** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **1**.

Moreover, residential problems of teachers affect their performance which obtained the weighted mean score of **3.86** with agree verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. The participation in collaboration research has enhanced their teachers development program which obtained weighted mean score of 3.69 with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **3**. Language of instruction affects teachers' performance obtained a weighted mean of **3.64** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **4**.

Furthermore, they try to maintain a careful and clean personal appearance was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **2.55** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **5**.

School heads perceived higher weighted mean score with **3.66** compare to the teachers perception with **3.33** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.56** implies that the schools heads and teachers level of effectiveness in terms of current status of teachers' job performance is agreeable.

Table 3.3
The Improvement of teachers Job Performance

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. They encourage class discussion of the students during every stage of instruction.	4.23	Agree	2	4.31	Agree	2	4.27	Agree	1
2. Their teaching efforts are directed toward motivating the thoughts of their students.	4.23	Agree	2	4.23	Agree	3.5	4.23	Agree	3
3. They try to satisfy their students when they ask questions in the classroom.	4.23	Agree	2	4.26	Agree	1	4.25	Agree	2
4. Motivated teachers have high performance that has low motivation.	3.31	Neutral	5	4.23	Agree	3.5	3.77	Agree	4

5. Motivated teachers create happy, relaxed but business like atmosphere in class	4.08	Agree	4	1.01	Strongly Disagree	5	2.55	Neutral	5
Average weighted mean	4.02	Agree		3.61	Agree		3.81	Agree	

This table shows the level of effectiveness of teacher's in terms of improvement of teachers' job performance. School Heads and Teachers perceived that an effective teacher encourage the class discussion of the students during every stage of the instruction which obtained the weighted mean of **4.27** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **1**.

Moreover, they try to satisfy their students when they ask questions in the classroom which obtained the weighted mean score of **4.25** with agree verbal interpretation on rank number **2**. Their teaching efforts are directed toward motivating the thoughts of their students which obtained weighted mean score of **4.23** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **3**. Motivated teachers have high performance that has a low motivation obtained a weighted mean of **3.64** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **4**.

Furthermore, they motivated teachers create happy, relaxed but business like atmosphere in class was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **2.55** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number **5**.

School heads perceived higher weighted mean score with **4.02** compare to the teachers perception with **3.61** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **3.81** implies that the schools heads and teachers level of effectiveness in terms improvement of teachers job performance is agreeable.

Table 3.4
Teachers' Subject Mastery

Indicators	School Heads			Teachers			Total		
	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank	WM	V.I	Rank
1. Knowledge of subject matter affects teachers' job performance	4.23	Agree	5	4.30	Agree	2	4.27	Agree	5
2. They respect the ideas of others and express a willingness to learn from them.	4.38	Agree	2	4.35	Agree	3	4.37	Agree	2
3. They provide guidance in their support time to the students.	4.38	Agree	2	4.29	Agree	4.5	4.34	Agree	3

4. They consider teaching as an opportunity of service for students.	4.31	Agree	4	4.29	Agree	4.5	4.30	Agree	4
5. They have adequate knowledge of subject matter in the courses they teach.	4.38	Agree	2	4.76	Strongly Agree	1	4.57	Strongly Agree	1
Average weighted mean	4.34	Agree		4.40	Agree		4.37	Agree	

This table shows the level of effectiveness of teacher's in terms of teacher's subject mastery. School Heads and Teachers perceived that an effective teacher have an adequate knowledge of subject matter in the courses they teach which obtained the weighted mean of **4.57** with verbal interpretation of strongly agree on rank number 1.

Moreover, they respect the ideas of others and express a willingness to learn from them which obtained the weighted mean score of **4.37** with agree verbal interpretation on rank number 2. They provide guidance and support time to the students which obtained weighted mean score of **4.34** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number 3. They consider teaching as an opportunity of service for students which obtained a weighted mean of **4.30** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number 4.

Furthermore, the knowledge of subject matter affects teachers' job performance was the least indicator which obtained the weighted mean score **4.27** with verbal interpretation of agree on rank number 5.

Teachers perceived higher weighted mean score with **4.40** compare to the school heads perception with **4.34** weighted score mean. The composite mean of **4.37** implies that the schools heads and teachers level of effectiveness in terms improvement of teachers job performance is agreeable.

4. The significant difference between the perceptions of two sets of respondents on teachers' performance in teaching.

Table 4
Differences between the Perception of the School Heads and teachers on Teacher's Performance in Teaching.

Variable	Critical Value	Computed Value	Remarks	Decision
				(H ₀)
Deadlines/ Time Pressure	4.303	0.073	No Significant	Accept
Workloads/Extra	4.303	0.285	No	Accept

Curricular Activities			Significant	
School Management	4.303	0.302	No Significant	Accept
Management of Student's Behavior	3.182	0.005	No Significant	Accept
Physical Environment/ Facilities	4.303	0.049	No Significant	Accept
Work relationship	3.182	0.003	No Significant	Accept

It can be observed from the table of the differences on the perceptions of the school heads and teachers on teacher's performance in teaching.

On deadlines and time pressures, the computed value are **0.073** is less than the critical value of **4.303** at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted thus, there are no significant differences on the perceptions of the school heads and the teachers on the teachers' performance in teaching.

On the workloads and extra- curricular activities, the computed value of **0.285** is less than the critical value of **4.303** at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, thus; there are no significant differences on the perception of the school heads and the teachers on the teachers' performance in teaching.

On the school management, the computed value of **0.302** is less than the critical value of **4.303** at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, thus; there are no significant differences on the perception of the school heads and the teachers on the teachers' performance in teaching.

On the management of student's behavior, the computed value of **0.005** is less than the critical value of **3.182** at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, thus; there are no significant differences on the perception of the school heads and the teachers on the teachers' performance in teaching.

On the physical environment and school facilities, the computed value of **0.049** is less than the critical value of **4.303** at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, thus; there are no significant differences on the perception of the school heads and the teachers on the teachers' performance in teaching.

On the work relationship, the computed value of **0.003** is less than the critical value of **3.182** at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, thus; there are no significant differences on the perception of the school heads and the teachers on the teachers' performance in teaching.

Teachers Effectiveness Enhancement Program

TRAINING PROPOSAL	
I. Title of the Training:	
“Enhancement Program for Secondary Teachers on Ways of Improving Teaching and Identifying Areas of Development”	
II. Target Participants and Number of Participants:	
10 Secondary Teachers per school	
III. Proposed Date and Venue	
Venue: Assigned by the Division Office Date: January, 2023 onwards	
IV. Funding Source:	MOOE/ Canteen Fund
V. Proposed Budget:	Php. 10,000.00
VI. Registration Fee:	Php.300.00
VII. Proponent:	Tanauan City Division
VIII. Rationale:	
<p>The Division Enhancement Program for Secondary Teachers on Ways of Improving Teaching and Identifying Areas of Development” aims to enhance the teachers’ ability to become effective in teaching.</p> <p>It also aims to provide an appropriate and well- planned program for teachers which includes giving them opportunities to grow and is designed to meet the diverse needs of all learners.</p> <p>This enhancement program is the key in meeting today’s educational demand.</p>	
IX. Objectives	
At the end of the three day training, the participants are expected to:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reinforced and enhanced teaching practices that will continue to improve student learning. 2. Provide meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that have a profound effect on the learning that occurs in the classroom. 3. Teachers should be equipped with an understanding and in depth knowledge to nurture their enthusiasm in teaching. 	
X. Training Content and Methodologies	Assigned by the Division Office

XI. Expected Output

Teachers Instructional Strategy Plan/Report: Accomplishment\ Coaching and Mentoring Form

DISCUSSION

The researcher created the teachers effectiveness enhancement program in accordance with the data collected. It has an expected output that the teachers will generate a teachers instructional strategy plan/report: accomplishment\ coaching and mentoring form which aim to reinforce and enhance teaching practices that will continue to improve student learning, provide meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that have a profound effect on the learning that occurs in the classroom and teachers should be equipped with an understanding and in depth knowledge to nurture their enthusiasm in teaching. As said by Panda and Mohanty, good teachers are essential for the effective functioning of the education system and for improving the quality of learning process by proper development design to measure the necessary factors among skills and attitude to develop by teachers with the support of more activity oriented programs provided by the division office.

Conclusions

With reference to the body's of data collected, the following conclusions were drawn by the researcher:

1. That the results of this research in length of teaching experience is one year to five years as revealed as rank number 1, this implies that they are in their early ages which can be able to use modern method of teaching to make it more interesting and attractive to student and also teachers who are energetic, with vigour to utilize modern approaches of teaching. The educational attainment revealed that most of the secondary teachers are masters' degrees; this implies that many teachers choose to return to school and obtain a master's degree that allows honing their abilities and becoming expert educators. Majority of the teachers are attending in service training this implies that teachers were well updated with better ways of undertaking their subjects. But more attendance in higher levels is required to enable them to undertake the same at least once a year.
2. The public secondary teachers perceived that the factors affecting teacher's job performance in terms of career related factors and non-career related factors were highly stressful.
3. The public secondary teachers generally agree in terms of the level of effectiveness of teachers in terms of teaching methodology, current status of teachers' job performance and teachers' subject mastery.
4. Since the perceptions of two groups of respondents with regard to the cited variables related to the factors affecting teachers' job performance are generally showing no significant difference, it could be concluded that the school heads and secondary teachers possess common and similar

factors that affect their job performance. In one way or another a teacher's performance is propped up when he or she is feeling comfortable in an environment that avoids oppression analysis results.

Recommendations

The insights that resulted from the research and the conclusions drawn from the body's of data collected, led in the formulation of the following recommendations and suggestions.

1. A similar study like this one could be also done using secondary school heads and teachers in the private schools of the district or division. Also, a study like this could be made using the secondary public school teachers of the division giving focus on the different items of evaluation.

2. It could also be recommended that the particular division conduct more quality circles intended for school teachers to regularly evaluate or assess the job performance of the teachers that could improve the division's educational system.

3. The present teacher writer also recommends another set of variables or categories to be used in identifying the factors that affect the teachers' job performance in the area.

4. It could also be suggested that continuous enrichment program activities, quality circles and intensive programs be given to explore the minds of the teachers in the different modern ways of effective teaching and be more motivated to do their job.

5. The teachers should be physically and emotionally ready to teach to promote quality education to the learners.

6. Secondary teachers should attend an Enhancement program, specifically an Enhancement program on nurturing their enthusiasm in teaching.

7. The researchers recommended to the future researchers to use references from national libraries to grasp more resources about factors that affect teacher's job performance.

8. Future researchers must provide more useful information about the study by using other types of methodology in data gathering procedure.

9. Future researchers must also conduct the study at the private schools to have at least different areas of knowledge and open up to different opinions and new ideas to the respondents.

10. The researcher recommended to the future researchers to widen the respondents to gather more ideas, opinions, perceptions and insights for the betterment of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All procedures performed by the researcher in this study were formally informed and asked the permission of the school and the author to use the collected data of teachers job performance to create the enhancement program for the public secondary teachers. The proponents also ensure that the respondents are willingly participating in gathering the data and the respondents had given

the right to withdraw their participation at any time. The respondents' participation in the study and responses to the questions are confidential. Data used in reports will be presented in a manner that prevents identifications of individuals and protects the respondents individual identity. The references used in this study were provided by the researchers to prevent plagiarism, and the study's findings were only utilized for research.

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